

Reclaiming the Constitutional Rights of Women in India

From Legal Protection to Social Transformation

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ABSTRACT

The Indian Constitution envisions equality and dignity for all citizens, yet women continue to face systemic barriers rooted in patriarchy and socio-economic inequality. This article examines the protection and promotion of women's constitutional rights through legal, social, and religious perspectives. It argues that true gender justice requires moving beyond legal safeguards toward transformative social engagement.

KEYWORDS: Women's rights, Indian Constitution, Gender justice, Patriarchy, Social transformation, Legal protection, Feminist theology, Human dignity, Equality, Structural inequality, Constitutional morality, Social justice.

01. Introduction

The Indian Constitution guarantees women the right to vote and participate in politics without discrimination. However, despite these rights, women remain underrepresented in governance due to entrenched patriarchal norms and the lack of safe political environments (Khan, 2015). Women in India often face unequal status in employment, education, and family life.

The 1974 report *Towards Equality* highlighted systemic barriers and called for improved employment opportunities, recognition of unpaid domestic labour, and protection for women as mothers (Mazumdar, 1994). Post-independence, especially after 1977, India witnessed a revival of women's movements. These movements broadened their focus to include issues such as violence, the rural economy, ecology, and cultural identity, pushing for comprehensive social reforms and challenging traditional development models.

The Indian Constitution is not merely a legal document; it reflects a dialogue between leadership and the public, shaped by Gandhian ideals, postcolonial aspirations, and socio-economic realities (Ishwara Bhat, 2019). Constitutionalism in India is rooted in social thought that emphasises

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participatory governance, justice, and moral responsibility. While the Fundamental Rights are enforceable in courts, the Directive Principles of State Policy guide governance toward social welfare. Scholars note that the implementation of rights and directives reflects the ancient Indian concept of *dharma*, blending duty and justice (Reddy, 1980).

The judiciary plays a pivotal role in bridging the gap between law and lived experience. Through Public Interest Litigations (PILs), courts have expanded the scope of rights to include environmental protection, education, and gender equality. However, access to justice remains limited, often benefiting those with social and economic privilege, raising concerns about elitism in legal enforcement (Liebman, 1985). India's legal system strives to reconcile Western ideals of formal equality with the realities of caste, religion, and gender divisions. Affirmative action policies, such as reservations, translate constitutional guarantees into tangible benefits, though they frequently encounter political and social resistance.

02. Constitutional Framework for Women's Rights

India's constitutional framework for women's rights is comprehensive, aiming to ensure equality, protection, and empowerment through multiple provisions. Article 14 guarantees equality before the law and equal protection under it and has been used by courts to challenge discriminatory laws and practices rooted in personal laws or patriarchal norms, particularly in education and employment (Kalpakam, 1997). Article 15 prohibits discrimination on the grounds of religion, race, caste, sex, or place of birth, while Clause (3) empowers the State to make special provisions for women and children, enabling affirmative action such as reservations in education and employment and protective labour laws (Khan, 2015). Article 16 ensures equality of opportunity in public employment, promoting gender-inclusive hiring practices in government services (S. Waseem Ahmad and M. Ashraf Ali, 2006). Article 21, interpreted broadly, protects the right to life and personal liberty, including dignity, privacy, and freedom from violence, forming the basis for landmark judgments on sexual harassment, domestic violence, and reproductive rights (Bharti Chhibber, 2018).

The Directive Principles of State Policy further strengthen women's rights. Article 39(a) directs the State to ensure men and women have equal right to an adequate means of livelihood, while Article 39(d) guarantees equal pay for equal work, shaping labour laws and gender wage parity policies (Khan, 2015). Article 42 mandates just and humane work conditions and maternity relief, underpinning legislation such as the Maternity Benefit Act and protections for women in hazardous industries.

Judicial interventions have been critical in bridging gaps between constitutional guarantees and lived realities. In *Vishaka v. State of Rajasthan* (1997), following the gang rape of social worker Bhanwari Devi, the Supreme Court established guidelines to prevent workplace sexual harassment, invoking international conventions (CEDAW) to fill legislative gaps and affirming Articles 14 and 21 (Agarwal, 2011). In *Joseph Shine v. Union of India* (2018), the Court struck down Section 497 IPC, which criminalised adultery only for men, upholding Articles 14, 15, and 21 and reinforcing women's moral agency (Tanja, 2016). Similarly, in *Laxmi v. Union of India* (2013), the Court addressed acid attacks, leading to stricter regulations and recognition of acid violence as gendered, expanding protections under Article 21 (Tanja, 2016).

Institutional mechanisms such as the National Commission for Women (NCW) play a crucial role in reviewing legal safeguards, addressing grievances, and promoting awareness (Vijayawargiya, 1992). Nevertheless, constitutional guarantees are often undermined by religious personal laws governing marriage, divorce, inheritance, and guardianship, which continue to perpetuate gender inequality (Parashar, 2008). While a Uniform Civil Code (UCC) could standardize rights, its current formulation has raised concerns about political motives and insufficient protection for women (Menon, 2014). Despite a robust constitutional framework, enforcement remains uneven, and women continue to face systemic barriers in accessing justice, with areas such as Hindu women's property rights still constrained by traditional interpretations despite statutory reforms (Patel, 2006).

03. Barriers to Realisation

Deep-rooted patriarchal values continue to shape societal expectations, limiting women's autonomy and reinforcing traditional gender roles. Cultural, religious, and literary traditions often normalise male dominance and female subordination, (Garg & Kumar, 1995) while family members and community leaders act as gatekeepers, restricting women's mobility, education, and employment (Vyas, 2025). As a result, women remain underrepresented in political decision-making and formal institutions, and historical exclusion from political spaces has limited the recognition of their contributions (Chary, 2012). Although legal provisions exist, enforcement is inconsistent and often inaccessible to marginalised women. Personal laws and fragmented legal systems can perpetuate inequality, particularly in matters of marriage, inheritance, and custody. Economic marginalisation further exacerbates disparities, with wage gaps, informal labour, and limited access to credit or land ownership undermining women's financial

independence. The promise of equal pay, as prescribed in Article 39(d), is often unmet in practice.

Feminist scholars describe Brahmanical patriarchy as a system where caste and gender hierarchies intersect to control women's sexuality and labour. Patriarchal norms restrict women's mobility, autonomy, and access to education and employment. The Sabarimala Temple controversy, where menstruating women were barred from entry, exemplifies how religious patriarchy regulates women's bodies (Thomas, 2019). Caste-based patriarchy imposes additional layers of oppression on Dalit women, who face discrimination from both upper-caste structures and, at times, within their own communities. Mainstream Indian feminism has often overlooked the unique struggles of Dalit women, highlighting the need for intersectional approaches (Arya, 2020).

Economic inequality intensifies gender disparities, as women from lower-income backgrounds frequently lack access to health care, legal aid, and education. Religious customs and personal laws also reinforce gender hierarchies; Hindu, Muslim, and Christian Personal Laws differ in their treatment of marriage, divorce, and inheritance, often to women's disadvantage. Reform efforts are frequently resisted due to political sensitivities and identity politics. Violence against women, including domestic abuse, sexual assault, and honour crimes, is widespread and underreported, with cultural stigma, fear of retaliation, and insufficient institutional support contributing to low reporting rates (Karp, Marwah & Manchanda, 2015). Despite laws such as the Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, (2005), enforcement remains weak, particularly in rural areas.

Wage discrimination persists across sectors, disproportionately affecting marginalised groups (Sengupta and Das, 2014). Limited access to formal employment, lack of childcare, and gendered expectations around unpaid labour exacerbate economic inequities. Women are also underrepresented in Parliament, State Legislatures, local governance, the judiciary, academia, and corporate leadership. Patriarchal norms, gender stereotypes, and societal expectations discourage women from pursuing public roles or leadership positions (Subramaniam, Krishnan, Bunda, 2014). Even with reservation policies and affirmative action, men continue to dominate decision-making spaces.

Policy-making often reflects patriarchal biases embedded in State institutions. Women's movement groups have criticised the vertically masculine structure of governance, which overlooks gendered power

dynamics and fails to incorporate feminist perspectives. NGOs and women's organisations have played a key role in training and supporting elected women representatives; however, systemic barriers persist (John, 2007). Gender budgeting and inclusive planning remain underutilised, and policies frequently fail to account for the specific needs of women, especially those from marginalised communities. While legal frameworks exist, social, cultural, and institutional barriers continue to limit the full realisation of women's constitutional rights.

04. Protection - Legal and Institutional Mechanisms

India's legal framework provides multiple protections for women, grounded in Articles 14, 15, 16, and 21, which guarantee equality, non-discrimination, and dignity. Specific legislation addresses domestic violence, workplace harassment, dowry, harmful cultural practices, and maternity rights. The Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act (PWDVA, 2005) provides civil remedies for victims of physical, emotional, sexual, or economic abuse within domestic relationships, including protection orders, residence rights, and monetary relief (Vihan, 2013). Similarly, the Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition, and Redressal) Act, (2013) institutionalises the Vishaka Guidelines, mandating Internal Complaints Committees in workplaces. The Dowry Prohibition Act, (1961) and the Pre-Conception and Pre-Natal Diagnostic Techniques (PCPNDT) Act, (1994) target harmful cultural practices, while the Maternity Benefit (Amendment) Act, (2017) increased paid maternity leave and introduced crèche facilities and work-from-home options for women in the formal sector.

Institutional mechanisms further support these legal frameworks. The National Commission for Women (NCW), established under the National Commission for Women Act, (1990) functions as a watchdog, reviewing legal safeguards, investigating complaints, and recommending policy reforms (Vijayawargiya, 1992). State Commissions for Women operate similarly at the regional level, providing legal aid, counselling, and public outreach. Women's movement groups have been instrumental in engaging with these bodies, shaping policy, and pushing for legislative reforms addressing violence and discrimination.

Despite these provisions, enforcement remains uneven and access to justice limited, especially in rural and marginalised communities. Many women are unaware of their legal rights or how to navigate institutional support systems (Mukherjee, 1975). Commissions often face structural limitations,

resource constraints, and restricted jurisdiction, operating within patriarchal state frameworks that reduce their transformative potential. Legal proceedings for gender-based violence or workplace harassment are frequently prolonged, with delays in trials and appeals contributing to low conviction rates and eroding public trust in the system. Violence laws, including the Domestic Violence Act, (2005) and Sexual Harassment Act, (2013), are often poorly implemented due to insufficient training, resources, and political will, while enforcement agencies may demonstrate insensitivity or hostility toward women's complaints. Consequently, even progressive laws fail to protect women effectively without robust and consistent implementation (Narain, 2013).

05. Promotion - Empowerment and Social Action

Empowerment is central to promoting women's constitutional rights, encompassing self-worth, agency, and control over resources and decision-making. It can be understood in stages: resistance, expansion of action, and consolidation of agency (Misra, 2006). Women's collectives and self-help groups have been instrumental in fostering social action, enabling women to challenge patriarchal norms, access credit, and participate in local governance (Saxena, 1994). Empowerment at the community level often catalyses broader social change, including shifts in gender roles and increased civic engagement (Gupta and Yesudian, 2006). Education is widely recognized as the most transformative tool for empowerment, enhancing self-confidence, decision-making capacity, and access to opportunities. The contemporary women's movement in India has emphasized education as central to feminist politics and development planning; however, disparities across caste, class, and rural-urban divides continue to limit its reach (Patel, 1998).

Economic empowerment through employment provides women with financial independence and strengthens their bargaining power within households and communities. Yet wage gaps, informal labour, and limited childcare support constrain women's full participation in the workforce (Misra, 2006). Political empowerment is equally critical, allowing women to influence governance and policy. Reservation policies have increased women's representation in local bodies, but leadership roles often remain male-dominated, and participation can be symbolic unless accompanied by genuine decision-making power and institutional support (Hazarika, 2006).

India's women's movement has evolved through a diverse network of NGOs, grassroots collectives, and advocacy groups. These organisations

have driven legal reforms, including the Domestic Violence Act (2005) and the Sexual Harassment Act (2013), and have acted as bridges between marginalised women and state institutions (Kalpagam, 2000). Social media platforms have introduced new forms of feminist expression and mobilisation; campaigns such as #MeTooIndia and #PinjraTod have challenged institutional sexism, democratised activism and enabling rapid organisation, particularly among urban youth. Local initiatives, such as the Gulabi Gang and Kudumbashree in Kerala, illustrate how community-based action can blend service delivery with advocacy, challenging caste, class, and gender hierarchies and creating sustainable models of empowerment (Kalpagam, 2000).

Faith-based engagement has also played a vital role in promoting gender justice. Feminist theologians and activists have reinterpreted sacred texts to affirm women's dignity and agency. Christian women's groups have challenged patriarchal readings of the Bible, advocating egalitarian interpretations, while Muslim women's organisations have used Islamic jurisprudence to argue for rights within shariah, emphasizing justice (*adl*) and compassion (*rahmah*) (Nair, 2017). Hindu feminist scholars have critiqued Brahmanical patriarchy and reclaimed female figures from mythology as symbols of empowerment. Movements like the Women's Wall in Kerala demonstrate how religious symbolism can challenge caste and gender hierarchies. Many women integrate faith and feminism, using religious identity as a source of legitimacy and strength in activism, challenging the notion that religion and feminist engagement are mutually exclusive. When rooted in critical theology and community dialogue, faith-based engagement becomes a powerful tool for advancing women's rights, especially in societies where religion shapes everyday life.

06. Transformative Constitutionalism

Rooted in the vision of Dr. B.R. Ambedkar, the Indian Constitution was designed to challenge caste-based oppression and institutionalise social justice. Justice D.Y. Chandrachud has emphasised that the Constitution embodies emancipatory constitutionalism, seeking to transform India's unequal, caste-ridden society into one grounded in freedom and equality (Thorat, 2024). Courts have interpreted constitutional provisions expansively to advance rights, particularly in landmark cases such as *Navej Singh Johar* (decriminalising homosexuality) and Joseph Shine (striking down the adultery law). This reflects a shift from textual interpretation to purposive, rights-based adjudication. Transformative constitutionalism is not unique to India; it aligns with broader Global South movements where

Constitutions are used to correct historical injustices and promote inclusive development (Hailbronner, 2017).

Despite its promise, transformative constitutionalism faces challenges from conservative institutions, slow judicial processes, and uneven implementation. Critics argue that without grassroots mobilisation and political will, constitutional ideals may remain aspirational (Dash, 1973). The Constitution was crafted with foresight, allowing adaptability to changing societal needs. Articles 14 (equality), 15 (non-discrimination), and 21 (right to life and dignity) have been interpreted to address contemporary issues, including gender justice, LGBTQ+ rights, and environmental protection (Shukla, 2014). Landmark judgments such as *Kesavananda Bharati*, *Vishaka*, *Navtej Singh Johar*, and *Joseph Shine* illustrate how judicial interpretation has evolved to uphold dignity, autonomy, and equality (Ahmad and Ali, 2006).

The framers envisioned the Constitution not merely as a legal code but as a tool for social transformation dismantling caste hierarchies, promoting gender equality, and ensuring justice for all citizens (Shukla, 2014). Its flexibility accommodates public interest concerns amid globalisation, privatisation, and shifting political landscapes (Viswanathan and Anuradha, 1994). Rights enshrined in the Constitution are thus instruments of transformation, as demonstrated in gender justice rulings like *Vishaka* and other cases challenging entrenched norms.

Realising these constitutional promises requires ethical responsibility from legal institutions, civil society, and corporate actors. Judicial sensitivity to marginalized voices, accountable governance, and adherence to ethical principles in law enforcement are essential. Social reform is further embedded in the Directive Principles of State Policy, which guide the State to reduce inequality and promote welfare. As Subhash Shukla notes, dismantling caste hierarchies and advancing equity requires legal reforms complemented by cultural and institutional shifts (Sukla, 2014).

Although gender equality is constitutionally guaranteed, implementation often lags due to bureaucratic inertia and patriarchal governance structures. Proactive state policies, gender-sensitive governance, and inclusive law-making that reflect women's lived realities are critical (Parashar, 2008). Women's movements, NGOs, and community organisations have historically driven both legal and social reforms from the *Vishaka* Guidelines to campaigns against dowry and acid attacks acting as watchdogs, mobilizers, and bridges between marginalized women and institutions (Patil, 2023). Faith-based organisations and feminist

theologians further contribute by reinterpreting religious texts to affirm women's dignity and challenge patriarchal norms, fostering gender justice within faith traditions and integrating ethical, social, and legal strategies for transformative change.

07. Conclusion

The Indian Constitution provides a visionary framework for gender equality, combining enforceable rights, Directive Principles, and transformative potential to challenge entrenched social hierarchies. Yet, as this essay has shown, legal guarantees alone are insufficient. Deep-rooted patriarchal values, caste and class hierarchies, discriminatory personal laws, economic marginalisation, and cultural norms continue to restrict women's autonomy and access to justice. While landmark judgments and progressive legislation have advanced women's rights, gaps in enforcement, bureaucratic inertia, and limited institutional capacity often impede their full realisation.

True gender justice requires a multidimensional approach that combines legal protections with social empowerment, community engagement, and inclusive policymaking. Education, economic independence, political participation, and grassroots activism are crucial for enabling women to exercise agency and challenge oppressive structures. Women's collectives, self-help groups, NGOs, and faith-based organisations have demonstrated the transformative power of collective action, bridging the gap between constitutional promises and lived realities. Feminist theological engagement further illustrates that cultural and religious frameworks can be harnessed to promote dignity, equality, and social reform, rather than serve as barriers.

The promise of transformative constitutionalism lies in its capacity to integrate law, ethics, and social action. When courts, institutions, civil society, and communities work in tandem, the Constitution becomes more than a legal code as it becomes a catalyst for dismantling caste, gender, and economic hierarchies. Achieving substantive equality for women in India is not merely a legal imperative; it is a moral and social responsibility. Only through sustained commitment, inclusive governance, and ethical action can the vision of a just, equitable, and empowered society be realized, ensuring that constitutional rights translate into meaningful freedoms for all women. □

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